

Supplemental Table S2 Top 20 enriched GO terms_CC

Category	Term	Count	%	PValue	Genes	List Total	Pop Hits	Pop Total	Fold	Enrichment Bonferroni	Benjamini FDR	
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	blood microparticle	17	12.68657	1.01E-15	FGB, SERPINA3, IGHM, TFRC, FGG, F13A1, C4BPA, A1BG, HPR, F2, CLU, CP, KNG1, HPX, C9, GC, IGHA2	131	145	20472	18.32187	2.47E-13	2.49E-13	2.37E-13
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	extracellular exosome	47	35.07463	9.16E-14	RPL4, RYR1, SERPINA3, IGHM, RAB5C, TFRC, SLC44A2, A1BG, AEBP1, HPR, PARK7, SERPINA6, CLU, THSD4, NAPG, FBLN5, KNG1, HPX, CLEC3B, EFEMP1, LMAN2, C9, SCRIN2, CA4, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, GC, MYH10, IGHA2, FGB, CYP2J2, RPS9, LUM, FGG, BGN, RRAS2, PA2G4, F2, CP, SOD3, CCT6A, NAGK, NACA, CAT, TPP1, PHPT1, CPVI	131	2218	20472	3.311504	2.26E-11	1.13E-11	1.08E-11
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	extracellular region	35	26.1194	2.82E-07	SERPINA3, PSMD14, TFRC, COL14A1, F13A1, LPL, C4BPA, A1BG, AEBP1, HPR, SERPINA6, CLU, FBLN5, KNG1, HPX, CLEC3B, EFEMP1, C9, EMILIN2, METTL7A, GC, IGHA2, FGB, LUM, FGG, BGN, PA2G4, F2, CP, ILF2, SOD3, ASPN, VCAN, CAT, COL6A6	131	2127	20472	2.571518	6.97E-05	2.32E-05	2.21E-05
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	extracellular space	31	23.13433	3.24E-06	SERPINA3, IGHM, TFRC, COL14A1, F13A1, LPL, C4BPA, A1BG, AEBP1, HPR, SERPINA6, CLU, FBLN5, KNG1, HPX, CLEC3B, EFEMP1, LMAN2, C9, GC, IGHA2, FGB, LUM, FGG, BGN, F2, CP, SOD3, ASPN, VCAN, CAT	131	1936	20472	2.502334	8.01E-04	2.00E-04	1.91E-04
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	platelet alpha granule lumen	7	5.223881	4.24E-06	FGB, SERPINA3, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, CLU, KNG1	131	67	20472	16.32722	0.001047398	2.10E-04	1.99E-04
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	Z disc	8	5.970149	2.37E-05	RYR1, PDLIM3, CSRP2, HOMER1, DNAJB6, NEXN, ANK2, RYR3	131	134	20472	9.329839	0.005842745	9.77E-04	9.29E-04
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	extracellular matrix	9	6.716418	2.53E-04	VCAN, EFEMP1, LUM, COL14A1, BGN, COL6A6, THSD4, FBLN5, ASPN	131	259	20472	5.430399	0.060680841	0.00858	0.008164
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	mitochondrion	22	16.41791	2.78E-04	PNPT1, NLRX1, POLDIP2, TFRC, SLC44A2, TACO1, GLRX5, TIMM9, AK4, ABAT, ANK2, PARK7, CLU, COQ7, NAPG, GLS, DHODH, MT-ATP6, PPA2, XPNPEP3, CAT, FXN	131	1437	20472	2.392516	0.066349728	0.00858	0.008164
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	mitochondrial matrix	10	7.462687	8.75E-04	MCEE, PNPT1, POLDIP2, PPA2, GLRX5, ABAT, AK4, PARK7, FXN, GLS	131	390	20472	4.007046	0.194520067	0.024025	0.022858

GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	focal adhesion	10	7.462687	0.001563	AKAP12, RPL4, LASP1, RPS9, CSRP2, TRIP6, CAT, PACSIN2, RRAS2, NEXN	131	424	20472	3.685727	0.320541452	0.038616	0.03674
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	lysosomal lumen	5	3.731343	0.003286	VCAN, LUM, BGN, TPP1, GC RPL4, HDLBP, PARK7, IFIT1, CLU, LCLAT1, GLS, AKAP12, EFTUD2, PREX1, PPP1R13L, PLS3, KPNA4, LRRFIP1, KPNA3, EIF5A, RPS9, USP7, ANK2, PPA2, CAT, PHPT1, FXN, CES1, PFKFB2,	131	96	20472	8.139313	0.556518915	0.073797	0.070211
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	cytosol	50	37.31343	0.004051	HSP90AB4P, PSMD14, WBP2, TYMP, PDLIM3, SNX2, DNAJB6, IFI16, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, GC, MYH10, STAT5B, PNPT1, HOMER1, DHODH, ARCN1, CCT6A, COPS6, EIF3M, NAGK, DNAJA4, XPNPEP3, TRIP6, AAK1	131	5477	20472	1.426646	0.633098515	0.083386	0.079335
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	Golgi lumen	5	3.731343	0.004682	VCAN, LUM, BGN, F2, SOD3 RPL4, RYR1, TFRC, SLC44A2, CLU, LCLAT1, NAPG, EFTUD2, SNX2, DNAJB6, IFI16, LMAN2, CA4, MYO18A, METTL7A, EIF5A, RPS9, RRAS2, ANK2, PA2G4, ILF2, COQ7, RPL3L, ARCN1, VCAN, PRPF6, DNAJA4, CAT	131	106	20472	7.371453	0.686245009	0.085949	0.081773
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	membrane	28	20.89552	0.004872	PDLIM3, TMOD3, TBCD, NEXN, ESAM, PARK7 RBM3, EFTUD2, PRPF6, U2AF2, DHX15	131	2547	20472	1.71798	0.700673406	0.085949	0.081773
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	adherens junction	6	4.477612	0.005227	PDLIM3, TMOD3, TBCD, NEXN, ESAM, PARK7	131	175	20472	5.357993	0.725950213	0.086071	0.081889
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	spliceosomal complex	5	3.731343	0.008104	RBM3, EFTUD2, PRPF6, U2AF2, DHX15	131	124	20472	6.301404	0.865993311	0.125107	0.119029
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	endoplasmic reticulum lumen	7	5.223881	0.013536	VCAN, COL14A1, FGG, F2, CP, KNG1, CES1	131	306	20472	3.574914	0.965477069	0.188749	0.179579
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	endoplasmic reticulum	15	11.19403	0.013755	FGB, SACM1L, RRAS2, ABCA8, PARK7, TECRL, CLU, LCLAT1, ARCN1, CLGN, DDRKG1, SOAT2, CAT, METTL7A, CES1	131	1142	20472	2.052646	0.967322484	0.188749	0.179579
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	mitochondrial intermembrane space	4	2.985075	0.019688	PNPT1, TIMM9, CAT, PARK7	131	90	20472	6.945547	0.992638974	0.254882	0.242499
GOTERM_CC_DIRE CT	cell surface	10	7.462687	0.020638	FGB, IGHM, TFRC, LMAN2, FGG, CA4, MYO18A, BGN, LPL, CLU	131	638	20472	2.449448	0.994206302	0.254882	0.242499
